

**INTERNATIONAL DAY OF THERMAL
SPRAY ALGERIA
26 NOVEMBRE 2025**

President's word

Prof. YOUNES Rassim

It is with great pleasure and a deep sense of pride that I address you on the occasion of the first edition of the International Day of Thermal Spray (IDTS 2025), organized by our university.

This scientific event marks an important milestone in promoting applied research and technology transfer in the field of thermal spray processes, an area with high potential for modern industries.

The University of Béjaïa has always been committed to fostering scientific excellence and supporting initiatives that encourage collaboration among researchers, educators, doctoral students, and socio-economic partners. Through this event, we reaffirm our determination to build bridges between the academic world and the industrial sector, in the service of innovation and sustainable development.

I warmly commend the organizers for their efforts, the invited speakers for their valuable contributions, and all participants whose presence reflects the vitality of our scientific community.

I wish you all fruitful discussions and great success for this first edition of IDTS 2025.

Plenary Speaker**Emeritus Professor, University of Limoges (France)**

Prof. Lech Pawlowski is an Emeritus Professor at the University of Limoges, France, and a member of the Institute of Research on Ceramics (IRCER – UMR CNRS 7315). He received his Ph.D. in Engineering from the Wrocław University of Science and Technology (Poland) in 1980, where he also obtained his habilitation in 1989. After several years of research in plasma spraying and coating technologies, he joined the University of Limoges in 1992, where he developed extensive research and teaching activities in the field of thermal spray coatings.

His scientific work focuses on surface engineering, thermal spraying processes, suspension and solution plasma spraying, and functional coatings for industrial and biomedical applications. Prof. Pawlowski is the author and co-author of more than 260 scientific papers and several books, including the widely recognized *The Science and Engineering of Thermal Spray Coatings* (second edition, Wiley, 2008) and *Physical Deposition Methods for Films and Coatings* (Springer, 2025).

Over his career, he has significantly contributed to advancing knowledge in materials processing, coating microstructure–property relationships, and the development of new plasma-sprayed materials. He has supervised numerous Ph.D. theses and collaborated with many industrial and academic partners worldwide.

Prof. Pawlowski is internationally recognized as one of the leading experts in the field of thermal spray technology and has been actively involved in international conferences, editorial boards, and scientific committees related to surface engineering and advanced coatings.

Sponsoring

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to Mr. Evgeny Urazov, Managing Director at Sharklin Tech, for his outstanding participation in IDTS 2025 and for the high-quality presentation of the ThermCalc software. With his strong background in industrial processes, his rich international experience—including at globally recognized companies—and his clear passion for R&D, Mr. Urazov delivered a presentation that was not only informative and inspiring but also fully aligned with the scientific objectives of our event.

His contribution shed valuable light on the advanced capabilities of ThermCalc, its impact on thermal analysis and materials modeling, and the new perspectives it offers for researchers and industry professionals working in the field of thermal spray and beyond. We greatly appreciate his commitment, his availability, and his willingness to share his expertise with our scientific community.

We sincerely thank him for his valuable contribution to the success of IDTS 2025 and look forward to future collaborations in the next editions of our conference.

Scientific Committee

- | | |
|------------------------------|------------------------------|
| 1- Pr PAWLOWSKI Lech | U-Limoge France |
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| 3- Dr YOUNES Rassim | U-Bejaia Algeria |
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Composition of the Organizing Committee

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| 3- BOUDJIT Sarra | U-Bejaia |
| 4-KHIMA Salim | U-Bejaia |
| 5- HARA Hamza | U-Bejaia |
| 6- IKHLOUFI Malika | U-Bejaia |

Table of contents

1.	Mohamed TAIBI, Synthesis and characterization of a geopolymer based on Algerian illite-montmorillonite	1
2.	Hana TOUATI, Integrating artificial intelligence into powder synthesis and thermal spray coating: challenges and opportunities	2
3.	Abdelkader SAILA, Enhancing properties of carbone, copper and silver by thermal spraying of TiO ₂ powder	3
4.	Samuel El HADDAOUI, DEDp and LPBF additive manufacturing of a TiC-reinforced case-hardened steel matrix composite	4
5.	Marco LEON, Development and cold spray application of a feniticial high entropy alloy synthesized by mechanical alloying	5
6.	GIBAS Anna, Exploring cold spray as a deposition technique for sol-gel materials	6
7.	Fatah HADJI, Kinetic analysis, and microstructural characterization of eskolaite powder prepared by the citrate method	7
8.	Mohand Amokrane BRADAI, Influence of post-treatments on the mechanical and electrochemical behavior of a stainless steel coating.....	8
9.	Luis Enrique SANZ, Fabrication of Ni-Al porous coatings by cold gas spraying.....	9
10.	Lotfi FAGHI, Mechanosynthesis-driven tailoring of Fe-Ni alloy: structural and magnetic insights	10
11.	Abdelhamid SADEDDINE, Mechanical characterization of an alumina-based coating obtained by plasma spraying.....	11
12.	Amine REZZOUG, Optimizing cold spray parameters for mixed Al–Al ₂ O ₃ /nylon coatings on CFRP: failure and substrate damage analysis	12
13.	Rassim YOUNES, Synthesis of alumina powder by the sol-gel process.....	13
14.	HARA Hamza, Influence of sol-gel synthetic parameters on the physico-chemical properties of alumina powder	14
15.	ZADRI Hanane, Effect of activator chemistry on the strength development of blast furnance slag geopolymer systems: review	15

Table of contents

16.	Achaichia Sarra, Structural, optical and electrical properties of sprayed Al doped ZnO thin films: effect of Al doping	16
17.	A.Bachiri, Zinc alloys for the development of biodegradable stents with controlled biocompatibility	17

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Synthesis and characterization of a geopolymer based on Algerian illite-montmorillonite

ABSTRACT

Using Illite-montmorillonite (IMN), a naturally occurring clay in the Naima-Tiaret-Algeria area, as a raw material, this effort intends to develop geopolymers (GPIMN). To do this, we will calcine the clay to 700 oC. and then activate it alkaline using high concentrations of NaOH and Na₂CO₃. The IMN and GPIMN clays were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), infrared spectroscopy (IRTF), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and X-ray fluorescence (XRF). The study looked at how the efficiency of the Ibuprofen (IBP) adsorption process was affected by the starting concentration and how long the adsorption process took. About forty minutes was found to be the duration of the adsorption process. The models that were used were the Elovich, pseudo-first-order, and pseudo-second-order versions. The most accurate model for the current application is the pseudo-second-order model, with an R² value better than 0.99. Thermodynamic study demonstrates that the adsorption is directly proportional to the starting concentration. Thermodynamic models using Langmuir, Freundlich, and D-R were used to determine the adsorption capacity of IBP with IMN-GPIMN. These simulations validated that the adsorption capacity of IMN-GPIMN was 48.54–66.66 mg/g. Given that it has a significant connection with the heterogeneous surface function (R² value more than 0.93), the Freundlich model is thought to be the most appropriate for use. Both the raw and blended versions of the local clay had a significant ability to adsorb ibuprofen, which was more than that shown in previous studies.

Keywords: adsorption; clays; isotherms; kinetics; geopolymer; pharmaceutical pollutant.

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Integrating artificial intelligence into powder synthesis and thermal spray coating: challenges and opportunities

ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly applied in materials science to enhance both synthesis and characterization processes. This work offers a literature-based exploration of how AI techniques, such as supervised and unsupervised learning, may contribute to powder design and thermal spray coating analysis. Applications include the prediction of powder morphology, particle size distribution, and chemical composition from synthesis parameters, as well as the classification of microstructural images and forecasting of coating properties. These approaches aim to reduce experimental workload, improve reproducibility, and accelerate the development of advanced surface materials. By synthesizing recent research and technological trends, this study provides an informed perspective on the capabilities, limitations, and future directions of AI-driven materials development. Particular attention is given to the current challenges related to data availability, model interpretability, and the integration of AI tools into traditional experimental workflows. This contribution serves as a foundation for future experimental and computational research in smart coating technologies and highlights the potential of AI as a driver of innovation in surface engineering.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence; Machine Learning; Powder Synthesis; Thermal Spray Coating; Performance Prediction.

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Enhancing properties of carbone, copper and silver by thermal spraying of TiO₂ powder**ABSTRACT**

In this work, we have contributed by treating Carbone, copper and silver materials by spraying TiO₂ powder on their surfaces at a high temperature of around 700 °C. This promising technique was used for enhancing physicochemical properties of these materials, namely resistance to solution and catalytic effect, where they will be used as electrodes in electrochemical processes of producing hydrogen and for treatment of pollutants. The development of this type of materials presents a challenge because of the following characteristics: synthesis methods and conditions, yield and resistance to reaction media; and this from an economic and reliability point of view. We have prepared C/TiO₂, Cu/TiO₂ and Ag/TiO₂ by spraying of TiO₂ powder on heated precursor surfaces of C, Cu and Ag. We have examined the reliability and the performance of these materials simultaneously in the production of hydrogen by electrolysis of NaCl solutions and in the treatment of organic and mineral pollutants. We have studied their reliability, resistance to solutions and processes yields in simulated reaction media. This kind of economic and simple materials can be used in industrial plants.

Keywords: Metallic materials; C/TiO₂; Cu/TiO₂; Ag/TiO₂, thermal spraying.

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DEDp and LPBF additive manufacturing of a TiC-reinforced case-hardened steel matrix composite

ABSTRACT

Iron-Based Metal Matrix Composites (IMMCs) exhibit high specific stiffness, excellent wear and thermal resistance. These properties make IMMCs ideally suited for wear-resistant parts and high-temperature structural components such as gears, bushes and bearings. However, ensuring homogeneous dispersion of the reinforcement and reliable interfacial anchoring remains a major challenge (Chen S. 2024). TiC promote high hardness, low density, and excellent metallurgical compatibility with steels. As for the matrix, 16NCD13, a low-alloy case-hardening steel containing chromium and molybdenum, promotes the precipitation of mixed secondary carbides, thereby enhancing high-temperature mechanical strength (Chengru L. 2023). Additive manufacturing (AM), in particular laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) and directed energy powder deposition (DEDp), offers the possibility to design complex geometries composite parts with new microstructure induced by high cooling rate. However, achieving a homogeneous composite powder composition at the LPBF melt pool scale remains challenging. DEDp offers greater flexibility in the processing of powders but the larger melt pool combined with the need for coarser powder particles unmelt TiC.

To address these challenges, LPBF powders containing TiC nanoparticles were surface grafted onto spherical particles of 16NCD13 steel. For DEDp, a premixed composite powders were optimized to minimize dilution while maintaining suitable powder projection. Good density, crack-free microstructures, with a uniform distribution of reinforcements, were obtained. Metallurgical quality and precipitation by direct ageing heat treatment were investigated using advanced characterisation techniques including SEM/EDS, TEM and XRD.

Chen S. et al. 2024. "Iron-Based Metal Matrix Composite: A Critical Review on the Microstructural Design, Fabrication Processes, and Mechanical Properties." Acta Metallurgica Sinica.

Chengru L. et al. 2023. "Adding Cr and Mo simultaneously enhances the strength and impact toughness of TiC microparticle-reinforced steel matrix composites at high temperatures." Journal of Alloys and Compounds.

Keywords: Powder metallurgy, steel matrix composite; additive manufacturing.

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Development and cold spray application of a fenitcual high entropy alloy synthesized by mechanical alloying

ABSTRACT

The equiatomic high-entropy alloy (HEA) FeNiTiCuAl was successfully synthesized by mechanical alloying using elemental powders. After 50 hours of high-energy ball milling at 350 rpm, the powder exhibited a uniform morphology and homogeneous elemental distribution, as revealed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), with an average particle size of approximately 30 μm . X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirmed the formation of a single-phase solid solution with a face-centered cubic (FCC) structure. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis showed two endothermic peaks, associated with the release of internal stresses from lattice distortion, and a distinct exothermic peak at about 350 °C, which corresponds to a phase transformation. To reduce residual stress generated during the milling process, the as-milled powders were annealed at 200 °C and 300 °C. Cold spray deposition trials demonstrated that the powder annealed at 200 °C yielded a better coating performance in terms of density and homogeneity. These findings highlight the potential of FeNiTiCuAl HEA for use in coating applications through cold spray processes.

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Keywords: High Entropy Alloys (HEA), Cold Spray, Heat Treatment, Mechanical Alloying, FeNiTiCuAl

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Exploring cold spray as a deposition technique for sol-gel materials

ABSTRACT

The integration of sol-gel chemistry with cold spray technology provides a promising approach for producing functional oxide coatings with enhanced surface properties. The aim of this work is to demonstrate the feasibility of depositing sol-gel synthesized TiO₂, Al₂O₃, and SiO₂ coatings using cold spray and to evaluate their functional properties. Compared with techniques conventionally paired with sol-gel materials deposition such as dip or spin coating, cold spray enables obtaining superior surface roughness. The resulting coatings exhibited photocatalytic activity, superhydrophobicity, and self-cleaning behavior, demonstrating that cold spray deposition can produce multifunctional surfaces from functional sol-gel materials without compromising their intrinsic properties. Additionally, the research shows that cold spray method can replace the drying and calcination steps. This study establishes cold spray as a promising deposition technique for sol-gel derived coatings, expanding opportunities for advanced surface engineering and functional material design.

Keywords: cold spray; sol-gel materials; sol-gel synthesis; functional coatings.

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Kinetic analysis, and microstructural characterization of eskolaite powder prepared by the citrate method

ABSTRACT

Eskolaite (Cr_2O_3) was synthesized through a citrate-assisted sol–gel method using chromium(III) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and citric acid as starting precursors. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), interpreted using the three-dimensional diffusion-controlled Ginstling–Brounshtein kinetic model, revealed a critical crystallization stage that occurred during heat treatment at 1100°C , leading to the formation of a dark green powder. This thermal event enabled the evaluation of essential thermodynamic parameters, including activation energy (E_a), entropy change (ΔS), and Gibbs free energy change (ΔG). X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirmed the formation of a well-crystallized phase with a hexagonal structure assigned to the R-3c space group. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis revealed a distinctive nodular surface morphology.

Keywords: Eskolaite ; Citrate route; Crystallization ; TGA ; Ginstling–Brounshtein ; Nodular morphology .

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Influence of post-treatments on the mechanical and electrochemical behavior of a stainless steel coating.

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to produce thermally sprayed coatings on an A60-type steel substrate, aimed at achieving surface hardening while enhancing electrochemical properties.

Post-treatments were carried out at temperatures of 850°C, 950°C, and 1100°C. In this work, the deposited metallic layers consist of stainless steel alloys. The thermally treated coatings are compared with a marine-grade structural steel, namely BV Grade A (also referred to as E36 BV), classified by Bureau Veritas, an international organization specialized in certification, inspection, and testing. The characterization techniques employed include microstructural and morphological analyses, as well as electrochemical and microhardness testing. Electrochemical results indicate that the thermally treated stainless steel coating behaves as an anodic layer, thereby providing cathodic protection through a sacrificial anode mechanism in a marine environment.

Key words : Thermal spray coating; Post-treatment; Stainless steel; Electrochemical behavior

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Fabrication of Ni-Al porous coatings by cold gas spraying.

ABSTRACT

Cold Gas Spraying (CGS) is a low-temperature solid-state deposition technique that forms coatings through high-velocity particle impact and plastic deformation, offering advantages such as microstructure retention, reduced oxidation, and improved mechanical properties over conventional thermal spraying. In this work, CGS was investigated for the fabrication of porous nickel–aluminum coatings, commonly used as catalysts in diverse fields and typically produced by plasma spraying or other non-spray methods like powder sintering. Cryogenic ball milling at -120°C allowed the production of a 70wt% Ni-30wt% Al bimetallic powder with a lamellar Ni-Al microstructure and an average particle size of 55 μm . The CGS deposition onto low-carbon steel produced a coating with 6% porosity that largely preserved this microstructure, achieving an approximate deposition efficiency of 50%. The Ni content, however, decreased slightly to 64wt%, likely due to differences in the in-flight behavior of Ni-rich particles. Heat treatments at 450°C for 4, 8, and 24h led to the formation of various Ni-Al intermetallics, namely NiAl_3 , Ni_2Al_3 , AlNi and Ni_3Al , reducing free Ni and Al content to 19wt% and 14wt%, respectively, after 8h. Additionally, porosity increased with heat-treatment duration, reaching 21% in the sample treated for 24h, as a result of intermetallic formation and the associated loss of interparticle cohesiveness. The selective aluminum dissolution at 80°C in concentrated alkaline solution, performed on coatings heat-treated for 8h, progressed uniformly, penetrating 168 μm after 15min and the full coating thickness after 1 and 4h. This caused the aluminum-rich phases to be strongly affected, as reflected by their disappearance in the XRD patterns, and led to a more brittle, porous, and poorly cohesive structures composed of unreacted Ni and chemically attacked intermetallics.

Keywords: Cold Gas Spraying; nickel aluminides; porous nickel-aluminum coating; Raney nickel coating.

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Mechanosynthesis-driven tailoring of Fe-Ni alloy: structural and magnetic insights

ABSTRACT

The Fe Ni alloy was synthesized by high-energy ball milling in order to investigate the correlation between microstructural evolution and magnetic behavior. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Rietveld refinement revealed the progressive formation of a solid solution with nanocrystalline domains as a function of milling time, accompanied by significant lattice strain and crystallite size reduction. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) observations confirmed morphological changes and particle refinement induced by mechanical alloying. Magnetic characterization using vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM) showed a strong dependence of saturation magnetization and coercivity on the microstructural parameters, highlighting the interplay between grain size, lattice defects, and phase formation. The results demonstrate that mechanosynthesis is an efficient route for tailoring the structural and magnetic properties of Fe-Ni alloys, making them promising candidates for applications in magnetic devices and energy conversion systems.

Keywords: FeNi alloy; mechanosynthesis; magnetic properties; ball milling; structural characterisation.

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Mechanical characterization of an alumina-based coating obtained by plasma spraying

ABSTRACT

Ceramic composite coatings have emerged as an effective solution to meet the growing industrial demand for improving the reliability of components subjected to multiple stresses. The plasma spraying process is considered a suitable method for producing such coatings with excellent mechanical properties.

In this study, alumina-based coatings were deposited on stainless steel (SS 304) substrates using the plasma spray technique. The coatings were then subjected to a post-treatment at 900°C for one hour. Microstructural observations revealed that the thermal treatment reduced porosity and resulted in more homogeneous and denser microstructures compared to untreated coatings. Consequently, the functional properties of the coatings—namely hardness and corrosion resistance—were significantly improved relative to those of the untreated samples.

Keywords: Plasma spraying; Alumina coating; Heat treatment; Mechanical and electrochemical properties

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Optimizing cold spray parameters for mixed Al–Al₂O₃ /Nylon coatings on CFRP: failure and substrate damage analysis

ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre-reinforced polymer matrix composites (CFRP) are highly competitive materials due to their excellent mechanical properties combined with low weight. Recently, cold spray (CS) has been investigated to enhance the surface properties of CFRP. In fact, CS appears to be a good candidate for this purpose because of the low process temperature. However, the high velocity of the particles can cause severe fractures in the CFRP, which limits the build-up of metallic coatings. Therefore, this study is devoted to investigating the effect of gas pressure and temperature in the CS process on coating deposition. For this purpose, fracture analysis and coating build-up were examined using optical microscopy. The CFRP substrate consisted of a carbon–epoxy composite reinforced by a metallic mesh at the top layer. The feedstock powder used for cold spraying was a commercial Al–Al₂O₃ blend, mixed with 10 wt.% nylon 6-6. Coatings were deposited using a low-pressure CS system (Centerline) under varying spray conditions, with gas pressures ranging from 80 to 250 psi and temperatures between 300 and 400 °C. The results revealed that when the gas pressure is below 120 psi, particle adhesion to the CFRP is insufficient. At higher pressures, deposition improves, but severe substrate fractures occur. On the other hand, increasing the gas temperature enhances particle ductility and reduces interfacial damage up to 400 °C, above which nozzle clogging may occur. Given the low erosion resistance of CFRP and the limited temperature window, it can be concluded that coating build-up on CFRP using cold spray is feasible only within a critical velocity range, that is, above the adhesion threshold of the particles but below the erosion threshold of the CFRP.

Keywords: Cold Spray, Polymer matrix composites, Mixed powders, Coating Deposition, Substrate Damage

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Synthesis of Alumina Powder by the Sol-Gel Process.

ABSTRACT

Alumina gels were synthesized using the sol-gel method, which is a simple, cost-effective, and efficient process. The alumina gel was prepared from an aluminum nitrate precursor. A few grams of citric acid were added to both samples to promote condensation reactions. In addition to citric acid, chromium chloride was introduced into the second sample to obtain a doped gel.

A portion of the obtained gels was characterized by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The remaining gels were subjected to thermal treatments followed by grinding at various temperatures until two calcined and crystallized powders were obtained. The resulting powders were characterized using optical microscopy and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). The formation of Al₂O₃ was confirmed by the FTIR spectra, which exhibited characteristic absorption bands corresponding to aluminum–oxygen bonds. In contrast, the FTIR spectrum of the chromium-doped powder showed spectral shifts and entropy variations mainly attributed to the presence of chromium and its transformation at high temperatures (exceeding the applied thermal treatment of 1000°C).

Keywords: Sol-gel process; Alumina powder; Chromium doping; Thermal treatment

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Influence of sol-gel synthetic parameters on the physico-chemical properties of alumina powder

ABSTRACT

The Sol-Gel method, belonging to gentle chemistry, constitutes a particularly interesting approach for the synthesis of ceramic materials, in particular in the form of powders, fibers or thin films. This technique is strongly influenced by several synthetic parameters such as pH, temperature, duration of reaction, concentration of precursors as well as the choice of the complexing agent. These factors play a decisive role in the quality and final properties of the material obtained. In this work, a white alumina powder has been synthesized by soil-gel using aluminum nitrate as a precursor, ethanol as a solvent, and citric acid as a complexing agent. During the synthesis, the pH of the solution was followed at regular 10 -minute intervals in order to better understand the chemical evolution of the system. After training of frost, a first fraction was subjected to a differential and gravimetric thermal analysis (DTA/TGA). This analysis highlighted two main mass losses, respectively 51 % and 21 %, accompanied by two endothermic peaks and an exothermic peak, indicating the successive stages of decomposition of organic species. The second fraction of the frost was calcined at different temperatures with a view to obtaining a white powder. The analysis by diffraction of X-rays (XRD) carried out on this powder revealed the formation of a single crystalline phase, corresponding to alpha (- Al₂O₃), indicating a complete crystallization of the material after heat treatment.

Keywords: Sol-Gel; pH; Properties; Alumina; XRD.

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Effect of activator chemistry on the strength development of blast furnace slag geopolymer systems: review

ABSTRACT

The increasing production of Portland cement (PC), over 4 billion tons annually, poses environmental challenges due to high energy demands, fossil fuel use, and CO₂ emissions. Alkali-activated materials (AAMs), or geopolymers, offer a promising alternative thanks to their low carbon footprint, ambient curing, and good mechanical performance. Blast furnace slag (BFS), widely available and cost-effective, is a commonly used precursor. Many studies have investigated its use alone or with materials like metakaolin, fly ash, or recycled glass. However, the results vary due to differences in activator types, concentrations, and curing conditions. This review examines how activator types affect the mechanical performance of slag-based binders, aiming to identify optimal, sustainable formulations.

Keywords: Alkali-activated materials (AAMs); Geopolymers; Blast furnace slag (BFS); Alkaline activators; Mechanical properties.

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Structural, optical and electrical properties of sprayed Al doped ZnO thin films: effect of Al doping

ABSTRACT

Thin films and thermal spray coatings have attracted significant attention due to their potential applications in protective layers, optoelectronic devices, and energy-related technologies. This work reports on the preparation and characterization of zinc oxide (ZnO) thin films by spray pyrolysis on glass substrates. The effect of Al doping with 1% Al, 3% Al, 5% Al, 7% Al on the structural, optical and electrical properties of the obtained films was studied. The obtained films are characterized by different techniques such as X-ray diffraction (XRD), UV-visible. The results of the XRD characterization indicate that all the films have the polycrystalline hexagonal wurtzite structure with a preferred orientation (002). Spectroscopic measurements in the UV-VIS-IR wavelength range were found to give good average transmittance values of about 80% in the visible zone with a band gap energy of about 3.2 eV. These results demonstrate that controlled doping can significantly improve the performance of ZnO thin films, making them promising candidates for optoelectronic and photovoltaic applications.

Keywords: ZnO, thin films, pyrolysis spray, XRD, Al doping.

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Zinc alloys for the development of biodegradable stents with controlled biocompatibility

ABSTRACT

Zinc-based alloys have emerged as promising candidates for biodegradable implants, notably cardiovascular stents, due to their intrinsically lower corrosion rate than magnesium alloys. In this study, a new biodegradable alloy Zn-5Mg and Zn-5Mg-xAl (1wt% Al, 3wt% Al, and 5wt% Al).

The experiments were carried out using Zn-5Mg-xAl alloys with a fixed total sample mass of 4 grams. High-purity powders of zinc, Magnesium and aluminum, each with a purity of approximately 99.99%, were utilized. The homogeneous mixture of these powders was compacted using a manual hydraulic press (SPECAC-GS2511) applying a uniaxial pressure of 10 tonnes. The resulting compacted specimens were dense pellets with dimensions of 20 mm in diameter and 2 mm in height.

The structure of pure zinc is generally coarse; however, adding magnesium and copper helps refine it. These elements act as grain refiners by forming intermetallic phases within the zinc matrix, which restricts grain growth and promotes a more uniform microstructural distribution. The addition of magnesium led to a marked improvement in the hardness of zinc. Likewise, incorporating aluminum further enhanced the hardness of the zinc alloy, emphasizing the beneficial effect of magnesium and aluminum additions on its mechanical properties. Electrochemical tests in Hank's solution after one hour of immersion revealed that adding magnesium and aluminum caused a slight positive shift in the corrosion potential, accompanied by a reduction in corrosion current density, wear resistance improves as the aluminum concentration increases.

Keywords: biodegradable, corrosion, homogeneous, wear, microstructure

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Mapping the application of transferred arc plasma welding in the repairing of hot work dies.

ABSTRACT:

Mechanical forming processes are responsible for the manufacture of a wide range of products. These processes yield high productivity of standardized parts, characterized by excellent mechanical properties. Actions that improve efficiency and reduce the environmental impact of production are crucial for the sector's growth [1]. It is estimated that up to 30% of the manufacturing cost of a part is attributed to tooling [2]. The manufacture of molds and dies is a complex and expensive process, making it essential to ensure their maximum possible lifespan. These tools are subjected to extreme conditions of use and often present failures due to wear, fatigue and plastic deformation [3]. A search on the Web of Science platform 131 works related to die and mold repair were selected.

It was observed that most studies use a laser as an energy source for material fusion, accounting for approximately 58% of the studies. Arc additive manufacturing techniques also stand out, with 14% of the cases. Plasma transferred arc (PTA) welding has been employed in only 2% of the selected scientific works. There is a significant opportunity for this technique. Plasma welding offers a good compromise between the desirable characteristics for repairing parts. It provides better control of heat input than conventional arc welding processes. Its cost is lower than laser welding and it is less complex to use. Powder can be used for feeding, allowing the use and customization of different alloys [4]. It is concluded that there is room to explore the potential of PTA welding for repairing molds and dies.

Keywords: Mapping, transferred arc plasma welding, hot work dies.

[1] Gao M, Wang Q, Li L, Xiong W, Liu C, Liu Z. Energy-based method for evaluating and reducing the environmental impact of stamping systems. *J Clean Prod* 2021;311:127850. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127850>.

[2] Chander S, Chawla V. Failure of Hot Forging Dies –An Updated Perspective. *Mater Today Proc* 2017;4:1147–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2017.01.131>.

[3] Jhavar S, Paul CP, Jain NK. Causes of failure and repairing options for dies and molds: A review. *Eng Fail Anal* 2013;34:519–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENGFAILANAL.2013.09.006>.

[4] Hirpara KP, Valaki JB, Chaudhari MD, Siddhpura MA. A comprehensive review on recent developments in materials and technological parameters for plasma transferred arc hardfacing process. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers Part E - Journal of Process Mechanical Engineering* 2024;238:1507–19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09544089231153363>.